

The Influence of Green Marketing on Consumer Behavior in Tamil Nadu: A Study

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Abstract: *Environmental issues are a hot subject today as governments and societies in every country have started to become more aware of green marketing issues. Here, the term "green" is indicative of purity. Green means pure quality and fair or transactional only. Green marketing is one of the strategies used by marketers to achieve sustainability. Green marketing is the development and sale of environmentally friendly goods or services. This helps build credibility, penetrate a new audience segment, and stand out from the competition as more and more people become environmentally conscious. Today's consumers prefer eco-friendly products, but their purchasing decisions differ due to lack of awareness about green marketing issues as well as knowledge about eco-friendly products. This knowledge enhances the knowledge of green production. Businesses need to know consumer attitudes and adapt innovative marketing solutions that focus on defining their expectations and meeting their needs. Marketers also realize the importance of green marketing concept. Green marketing strategy has great power to motivate both consumers and manufacturers to participate in saving the planet, and at the same time, profit from the potential of eco-friendly products while satisfying their needs. Although numerous studies on green marketing have been carried out around the world, very little academic research on consumer Behavior has been done. This study provides a brief assessment of environmental concerns and identifies consumers' green values, their level of awareness of environmental issues, as well as green environmentally friendly products and practices. This article highlights the impact of green marketing on consumer Behavior using a structured questionnaire.*

Keywords: Green Marketing, Green Products, Green Consumers, Consumer Behavior, Environmental issues, Eco-friendly, Tamil Nadu

I. INTRODUCTION

Green marketing -refers to the marketing of presumed environmentally safe products. It encompasses a wide range of activity, including the product modification, production process changes, sustainable packaging, and advertising modification. Since there are so many overlapping and conflicting definitions of green marketing, it is challenging to determine what it means. For instance, there are numerous social, environmental, and commercial definitions of the term. Environmental marketing and eco marketing are also synonyms. One of the many emerging marketing strategies is ecological, environmental, and green marketing. Additionally, the approach challenges existing marketing practices and presents a new perspective. With regard to the mismatch between today's practices in the market and the broader marketing environment, green, environmental, and ecological approaches are part of a larger group of approaches. As a term for sustainable development, "greener consumption" refers to environmentally friendly consumption habits. There are many benefits to this type of consumption, such as preserving the environment for future generations and reducing waste. With the help of environmentally friendly practices like the use of organic products, clean energy, and renewable resources, and a selection of goods made by companies with zero or nearly zero waste, it makes consumers share in the burden of solving environmental problems (zero-emission vehicles, no energy construction, etc.). When it comes to purchasing and discarding goods and services, consumer Behavior is the study of how people and groups make their decisions. Furthermore, the impact on customers and society is examined.

As people around the world become more aware of the effects of climate change and global warming, environmental protection and sustainable development are becoming more popular. Indian and international marketing trends will be shaped by this shift in consumer Behavior, which is a result of this issue. To remain competitive in the market, a marketer must be aware of these changing social trends and respond positively to them. Several large and small

businesses in India are responding to this shift in consumer Behavior by incorporating a green theme into their customer communications. There should be no restriction on the use of the green theme in marketing. If the company is to achieve zero emissions or contribute to reducing them, then the company and its employees must actively promote the idea. Environmental consumerism (green buying) is a type of eco-friendly Behavior that involves purchasing and consuming environmentally friendly products. There is a growing market for products that are "environmentally friendly" which gives companies an opportunity to include the term "environmentally friendly" in their value proposition. Indian consumers' environmental concerns are examined in this paper along with their knowledge of environmental issues, their awareness of environmentally friendly products, and the impact of income and education level, education, and the effect that they may have on consumers' decisions to make environmentally friendly purchases.

II. GREEN MARKETING

"Green" or "environmental marketing" encompasses any efforts aiming to foster social-ecological harmony through increased human contact while minimizing environmental effect. According to the AMA-American Marketing Association, green marketing refers to the promotion of ecologically friendly products. Green marketing includes a huge array of actions, including product modification, production process adjustments, package redesigns, and alterations to customer advertising. Other phrases linked to Environmental Marketing include green marketing and environmental marketing. Green marketing is implemented by businesses to address price or profit concerns. Consumers, businesses, and government agencies each play a critical role in implementation of green marketing. However, its implementation is hindered by customer ignorance, financial constraints, insufficient scientific understanding, the absence of rigid laws, and competitive pressures. The expansion of products as well as services that satisfy the needs of the client in terms of quality, performance, cost, and convenience without damaging the environment is green marketing.

III. THE GREEN CONSUMER AND GREEN PRODUCT OR SERVICE

Consumers in the USA and Europe have become more environmentally concerned in recent years. This growing pattern has extended to Asia, becoming more widespread. Consequently, the vast majority of the privileged in the world now think about environmental concerns. More people are choosing green products and services. A green product or service is defined as a product or service that won't hurt the environment or harm natural resources and can be recycled or conserved. As businesses understand that green products and services can be profitable, they are producing more green products and services. For a company, going green does not ensure that the environment will be saved, but it may be able to keep the business alive. Consequently, businesses must get information to understand and serve better green consumers.

IV. GREEN CONSUMERS

Green consumers can be classified as several different types. It's best to take into account some of their common features in helping businesses to better understand the market for products for environmental protection.

In general, there are four categories of green consumers:

- **Behavioral Greens** – These customers purchase only products services that help to improve the natural environment. They don't deem purchasing damaging to the environment. They incorporate enough eco-friendly practices in their life.
- **Think Greens** – These customers frequently purchase green products or services, but when time, cost, or financial resources intervene, they choose not to.
- **Potential Greens** – However, they may act environmentally friendly when influenced or encouraged by others.
- **True Browns** – These customers often avoid any firm that sells products or performs services with an environmental focus.

V. CONSUMER BEHAVIOR IN GREEN MARKETING

Understanding consumer Behavior has turned into a crucial component of green marketing. The goal of consumer Behavior is to investigate how customers make a purchase, arrange their needs, choose products, or execute particular actions in relation to a product or service. To assess the Behavior of prospective consumers towards a new product or service, it is essential to comprehend consumer Behavior. It is also extremely beneficial for businesses to find untapped prospects. Businesses who spotted this market void have manufactured eco-friendly goods and exploited this market facet. Companies that failed to observe customer Behavior, on the other hand, were unable to fill this hole in the market and were left behind. Understanding customer Behavior enables initiative-taking businesses to grow their market share by predicting changes in consumer preference.

VI. GREEN CONSUMER ATTITUDES AND BEHAVIOR

With the advent of green marketing, consumer Behavior has altered. They desire more eco-friendly products and services. Consumers are transforming their environmental worries into sustainable purchasing practices. People who care about the environment are altering their Behavior to benefit the environment. People felt a moral obligation to purchase green products. However, environmentally conscious individuals do not necessarily act in an environmentally responsible manner.

The relationship between income and environmental purchasing Behavior has been established. It was suggested that those with higher earnings can afford to spend more for green products. Additionally, there is a correlation between amount of education and environmental views and Behavior. It is argued that those with a higher level of education comprehend environmental issues significantly better and so act in an environmentally responsible manner.

VII. CONSUMER BEHAVIOR ANALYSIS

Consumer Behavior in the market is heavily influenced by the observation of customers from the time they are always in the marketplace up until they end up making their final purchase. Consumer Behavior, in other words, active investigation of the phenomenon whereby customers make purchase decisions and the conditions that lead to such decisions. When marketers know why an individual decides to select specific products or services over another, they can use that information to determine which products are in demand and which ones have become obsolete, which can allow them to design more powerful marketing strategies.

VIII. AIMS & OBJECTIVES

This research seeks to discover the perceptions of consumers of green values created by promoters' green marketing efforts and their impact on Consumer Behavior of eco-friendly products. Promoting environmentally friendly products and services is a fairly new concept known as green marketing. In order to minimize environmental damage, the products as well as services must be developed, manufactured, promoted, distributed, consumed, and disposed of sustainably. Environmentally friendly products are those that are manufactured with green technology and have no negative impact on the environment. There is a growing demand for green products, and customers are willing to pay a premium for them.

Moreover, green marketing evolution is spreading around the Indian market rapidly, and the concept has had a radical influence on increasing environmental awareness among the consumer population and changing consumer perception toward green marketing practices and products as well. Thus, the study also has the following objectives to fulfill —

1. Understanding how consumers are knowledgeable about eco-friendly products and environmental issues.
2. For this study, the goal is to learn consumers' perceptions of green initiatives in the production chain.
3. This study examines the role played by green marketing in the development of unique brands.
4. Identify whether consumers' pro-environmental concerns, awareness of eco-friendly products, as well as knowledge of environmental issues influence their buying of eco-friendly items.
5. Analyse the readiness of customers to pay extra for eco-friendly green products.

IX. HYPOTHESIS

1. Consumers have very little awareness of the concept of green products and marketing.

2. There is a willingness among consumers to purchase green products regardless of the level of academic qualification.
3. Green marketing encourages customers to pay a greater amount for green products.
4. Consumers are more likely to favor healthier products.

X. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Related study relies on Survey Method. In this context, we distributed 100 Questionnaires to various Institutions, members of SHG, and individuals. The samples were selected in and around Tamil Nadu. A web link can be sent to respondents via electronic means. The Internet can also be adopted as a method for circulating the survey. Data analysis using relevant statistical methods can lead to conclusions.

XI. DATA INTERPRETATION

Modern civilization places a greater focus on green marketing. Google Trends indicates that, relative to other countries, more searches for "green marketing" originated in India than in any other nation. Green marketing provides a paradigm for achieving economic growth, social justice, increased environmental stewardship, and enhanced governance. Nowadays, consumers favor ecologically friendly items, but their purchase selections differ due to varying degrees of ignorance regarding green principles. Any product that does not have negative effects on individuals, the surrounding ecosystem, and the consumer in the future is a green product. In addition, organically farmed foods have superior flavor and health benefits compared to their conventional counterparts.

XII. RESULT OF THE STUDY

Objective of this study is to explore the impact of consumer Behavior (CB) on green marketing(GM). A total of 100 questionnaires were collected from the respondents of Tamil Nadu through the use of a survey. This paper discusses the need for consumer education regarding environmental issues.

Consumer awareness of green products has been created, as we conducted our survey based on this and we found that 72% of consumers answered negatively about green products and 28% responded positively about awareness of green products.

Consumers tend to purchase green products more frequently. In our survey, 18% of consumers buy green products once a week, 34% frequently buy green products once a month, 28% purchase green products once a year, and 20% buy green products regularly when necessary.

Awareness of green products among consumers. Approximately 74% of consumers have average, 16% have low and 10% do not have any knowledge about green products, according to our survey.

An understanding of the dimensions of green products. According to our survey concerning the dimensions of green products, 58% of consumers responded that they are concerned about the environment, 30% responded that they are concerned about their health, 9% responded that they would use better quality products, and 3% responded that they were concerned about their personal status.

Acceptance of green products in the future. According to our survey, 52% of consumers intend to consider green products, 34% consider them occasionally, 13% consider them, but not in the near future, and 1% never consider them.

The willingness of consumers to recommend green products to others. Our survey indicates that 58% of consumers are willing to recommend green products to others, 30% are very willing, 11% are neutral, and 1% are unwilling.

Information about green products can be obtained from the following sources. According to our survey, 25% of consumers obtain information through television, 35% via social media, 10% via newspapers, 12% via magazines, and 18% via friends.

Consumers' preferred place to purchase green products. Our survey shows that 42% of consumers prefer to buy from local retailers, 33% prefer to buy from retail malls, 13% prefer to buy online and 12% prefer to purchase from factory outlets.

In advertisements, the focus is primarily on the greenness of the product and not on its performance. In our survey, 49% of consumers agree, 35% are not yet certain, 14% disagree, and 2% strongly disagree.

The consumer is prepared to pay extra for green products (GP). According to our survey results, 59% of consumers are prepared to pay little more for green products(GP), 38% are not prepared to pay more, and 3% are prepared to pay more.

The marketing element of green product purchasing Behavior. The results of our survey indicate that 42% of consumers choose products, 34% choose promotion, 16% choose packaging, and 8% choose place as a marketing element for green products.

There are several reasons why consumers are not ready to pay extra for green products(GP). According to our survey, 42% of consumers responded that the cost of the product is too high, 32% of consumers responded that they cannot see the benefits of the features, 22% of consumers responded that producers should pay for them, and 4% responded that the government has to pay for them.

The required level of satisfaction of consumers with green products. The survey indicates that 41% of consumers are neutral, 33% are satisfied, 23% are not satisfied, and 3% are not satisfied at all.

The repetition of green products. In our survey, 40% of consumers prefer to repeat sometimes, 28% prefer to repeat always, 28% prefer to repeat often, and 4% prefer not to repeat at all.

According to the above results, most respondents feel that they are environmentally responsible, while some are concerned about their health. There are some respondents who don't want to pay more if the price of green products increases in the future. Hence, consumer awareness and education contribute to increasing the knowledge of green products.

XIII. IMPACT ON THE ENVIRONMENT OF GREEN MARKETING

Green product marketing promotes consumers to utilize eco-friendly items and encourages manufacturers to create more. Advertising should be used to raise knowledge about the items so that individual purchasing patterns can be altered, so improving the environment. Innovation and competitiveness are the emerging problems of global competition, necessitated by environmental progress. Green products require expensive renewable and recyclable components. It involves a technology that necessitates substantial research and development expenditures. Consumers must be required to distinguish between eco-friendly and non-eco-friendly products.

XIV. SUGGESTIONS

A major goal of green marketing is preventing environmental pollution, as well as teaching people the value of reusable products. However, the producers don't market their products correctly or advertise them on the right platform, so they charge higher prices. The marketing and use of the product should grow, but its quality and cost should remain reasonable. Thus, it's recommended that producers disclose the amount split by the products they produce to ensure public transparency. Competition in the market affects the firm's activities greatly. Green marketing has made firms increasingly competitive by pushing them to incorporate greenness at every stage, from choosing the raw material to the end of the product life cycle. As a result, firms can gain competitive advantages in terms of economic standards, which helps build strong market leadership and helps consumers choose healthier products.

XV. CONCLUSION

In recent years, business ethics, environmental issues, sustainable development, and social responsibility have become increasingly important than ever for companies. Social media, newspapers, and word of mouth remain the leading sources of information for most of the respondents and should be utilized more for reaching out to the consumers regarding green products and practices. Consumers have been showing a more positive attitude toward green products, but as a result, the affordability and availability of such products is another concern. This implies that marketers should make green products available to consumers for their consumption, as customers have shown a willingness to buy green products if they are available. In the near future, green marketing will contribute to the creation, sale, and dissemination of awareness about the advantages of environmentally-friendly products, contributing to a better tomorrow. Rather than being an outsider to nature, we are a part of it. It is impossible for modern civilization to come up with a solution to the ecological problem without first examining its methods of living. The practical use and benefits of green products are guaranteed. Demonstrating competitiveness in the resolution of environmental issues. A

green product can be improved by asking and respecting the preferences and choices of consumers. The study has implications for marketers as well as consumers and makes a good case for the start of an era of green marketing at Tamil Nadu. Due to the study's geographical limitations, it is not generalizable, but it provides valuable insights into consumer behavior in relation to green products. Future research could focus on psychographic segmentation of consumers in terms of assessing their green values and preferences. The study can be done again on a bigger scale to learn more about how people act and to understand green phenomena.

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